

CHARACTERISTICS OF SPORTS ACTIVITIES IN THE TRAINING OF YOUNG VOLLEYBALL PLAYERS IN CHILDREN AND TEENAGERS SPORTS SCHOOLS

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Abstract: This article discusses the specifics of sports training and its content in the training of young volleyball players in children and youth sports schools.

Keywords: children and adolescents, adolescent sports schools, socio-economic, spiritual-moral, cultural-domestic, physical and psycho-functional, technical and tactical processes.

Introduction

The sacred duty of every human being and our society is to bring up children who have the meaning of life, to bring them up both physically and spiritually, to be loyal to their parents and the Motherland. Physical education in youth education and involvement in sports Physical education in classes, extracurricular activities, extracurricular activities training sessions for children and adolescents in sports schools plays a key role. Sport in the broadest sense is a competitive activity - a special preparation for it, the study of socio-economic, spiritual-moral, cultural-domestic, physical and psycho-functional, technical and tactical processes associated with this area. density.

The essence of the concept of "sport" is the desire of a person to overcome all obstacles and challenges and to expand the limits of their capabilities. Sport is a modern, super-mass social movement that "sharpens" the mind, lifts the mood, shapes a person physically, spiritually and spiritually, improves his "inner" and "outer" culture, and gives humanity infinite joy. So sport is a profound, multifaceted social factor.

Although the term "sports training" in sports practice is logically close to the term "sports training", they are fundamentally different. The term "sports training" has a broad meaning and refers to the athlete as a whole is a process aimed at preparing its activities for competition. "Sports training" is a goal-oriented process and has a relatively narrow meaning. As a result of regular sports training, a person's motor activity is formed, new forms of movement are formed, vital motor skills (running, jumping, walking, etc.), skills are improved, mental qualities (thinking, mind, will, attention, emotion, etc.) finds a pattern. Movement skills specific to a particular sport are improved. In sports training, various equipment, sports inverters and selected exercises are used as the main tool in general and special physical training. Volleyball as a sport leads to the full physical development of a person. Regular volleyball training improves all physical, technical, tactical and psycho-functional qualities. The technical and tactical skills of volleyball, which are performed over a long period of time (up to 1.5–2 hours) in different directions and speeds, form the general and specific endurance of the trainee. The individual, group and team actions performed in the game show the qualities of mutual support, mutual assistance and solidarity. The main purpose of the training process is to prepare athletes for the competition at a high level of "sports uniform" and to create opportunities for them to achieve high results in this competition. Specialized volleyball classes are held from the age of 10-12. However, the principle of universalization prevails when working

during training can lead to a loss of goals for the athlete and the coach. Therefore, it is important to ensure that the regularity of the multi-year training process is interrupted, without interrupting the various breaks. However, this continuity should be based on the fact that the training load is alternated with rest, recovery of working capacity.

It is this law that aims to mobilize all the resources of volleyball players during the competition. To do this, during the many years of training, the tasks, assignments and exercises related to physical, technical and

tactical training are gradually expanded to the maximum volume and intensity in the order of "easy to difficult", "simple to complex", "mastered from unmastered". is executed at the level of. In volleyball, as in other sports, the main means of training is exercise. They are very diverse. Therefore, they are categorized according to the level of solving certain tasks in the training phase. This classification is based on the competitive activities of young volleyball players. Accordingly, the exercises are divided into two main groups:

Competitive workouts are special, unique exercises that are unique to volleyball. In this case, the technical methods and tactical actions are performed in accordance with the conditions of the competition. The training exercises are aimed at facilitating, accelerating the acquisition of basic skills and ensuring their effectiveness and reliability. They consist of specific and general developmental exercises.

Special exercises are divided into two groups:
 preparatory exercises; Approaching exercises.

Preparatory exercises are mainly used in the training of special physical qualities. Approaching exercises are used in the process of mastering specific technical movements. All exercises are included in the training, depending on the direction. These preparations include: general physical; special physical; technical; tactical; integral

Each type of preparation has its own set of guidelines that can be used to solve the problem. However, exercises of one type of training are closely related to exercises of another type of training. For example, if a trainee does not have the necessary quality of agility, he will not be able to perform attacking techniques. In this case, it is advisable to provide exercises to improve the quality of agility. Because increasing the repetition rate of the attack kick is not effective in this case.

That's why children and teenagers are trained in sports schools:

- Training methods for young volleyball players
 the basics are learned;

In short, the involvement of physical education and sports in the education of young volleyball players plays a key role in physical education classes, extracurricular activities, out-of-school training in sports schools for children and adolescents. This means that the effectiveness of tools in training young volleyball players in volleyball movements often depends on the methods used. In addition, in each type of preparation, it would be appropriate if the sequence of tasks and types were carried out in a certain logical connection.

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